

Tracking the intracellular uptake of free labeled nanoclay Laponite by confocal Raman imaging technique through its chemical fingerprint

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Laponite is a nanoplateform that has been successfully used as a new biomaterial for drug delivery, tissue engineering and bioimaging at the nanoscale. In general, a deep knowledge of the mechanism interaction of the nanomaterial with biological components in a physiological environment is highly desirable for properly characterizing its therapeutic efficacy and toxicology. Up to now, the use of fluorescent dyes labelling both, the nanomaterial and cell components, has been a requirement to characterize the cell uptake and to visualize the entrance of the nanomaterial into the cytosol and the cell nucleus. The used fluorophores usually perturb the physiological medium and can interfere in the nanomaterial cell interaction. A new Raman imaging methodology to track the uptake and internalization of Laponite nanoparticles into J774 macrophages line cells is presented in this work. The combination of Raman spectroscopy and confocal microscopy provides direct information about the localization of the nanoparticle into the cell, through its unique vibrational fingerprint without labelling or adding dyes, and taking advantage of the fact that Laponite and biological molecules bands can be clearly differentiated. A mapping of the intracellular Laponite position can be performed by acquiring a Raman image at different distances from the focus (Z-planes) inside the cell. Thus, this technique allows univocal confirmation of the presence of the nanoclay in the cytosol, thus indicating the precise cellular region where the nanomaterial is located.

Keywords: Laponite, nanomaterial, nanocarrier, Raman imaging technique, nanoclay

Laponite, a synthetic layered clay, is a versatile non-toxic nanomaterial that has inspired extensive ways for the design of biomaterials with great potential in nanomedicine, from diagnosis and cell therapy, to regenerative medicine or tissue engineering, and bioimaging.¹ Laponite particles are disk-shaped with a high aspect ratio (25 nm in diameter and 0,92 nm in height) that stack together due to attractive electrostatic forces in solid-state. However, since Laponite is a swelling clay, under some specific experimental conditions, it can delaminate in water, forming a stable colloidal dispersion, useful for biomedical applications.

In general, the use of different nano-carriers, mainly nano-emulsions, liposomes, micelles, dendritic structures and carbon nanotubes among others, are reported to considerably improve the therapeutic efficacy of a drug, by the selective uptake of the nanomaterials.^{2, 3} In this sense, Laponite has shown its ability as an efficient platform for drug delivery, via ion exchange reaction, being the drug-release process highly sensitive to the acidic conditions of the environment.^{4, 5} Thus, this nanoplatform has been successfully used as a carrier system for chemotherapy drug delivery and other oncological applications, improving the therapeutic efficacy of the chemotherapeutic drug and avoiding cytotoxic effects to normal tissues, as compared with the free drug.⁶ Laponite is also useful in the field of bioimaging, working as a vehicle to transport insoluble and non-emissive dye molecules in water. When the nanoclay is combined with hydrophobic fluorophores at low concentration, the dyes show strong-fluorescence, acting as a probe to visualize different biological processes.⁷

To this end, a deep knowledge of the interaction of the nanomaterials with the biological components in a physiological environment is highly desirable to properly characterize its efficacy and toxicology. The use of fluorescent dyes labeling both, the nanomaterial and cell components, is mostly a requirement to visualize the entrance of the nanomaterial into the cell and its structures.

The nanosystem cell uptake is usually monitored through fluorescence microscopy, the most commonly used technique, specifically Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy (CLSM). In addition, the application of CLSM to nanoparticles is not always easy, since the size of the nanoparticle falls well below diffraction limit of optical microscopes.⁸ Differentiation of the nanomaterial cell-uptake mechanism, from the adhesion of the nanoparticle on the cell surface, is a key point to understand its role as bio-nanoplatform. Hence, information about the interaction between the nanoparticle and the drug, and the release of the drug in physiological medium or in the intracellular milieu, is not always univocal. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM), a free-label technique, can also be used to study the localization of the nanoparticle in the cell, however, the complex preparation process can irreversibly affect the condition of the sample.

Raman spectroscopy is a classical technique in analytical chemistry and material science, but, the use of this non-invasive spectroscopic technique in biomedicine has not been widely established until the last decade.⁹ The low efficiency of Raman scattering since only 1 in 10^8 photons are inelastically scattered, together with the difficulty to obtain straight forward information from Raman spectra of biological systems, where multiple scattered signals overlap, has delayed its extensive use. Even so, the fast development of technology, including high-quality lasers and optical elements together with more sensitive detectors, has increased the technical efficiency of the Raman spectroscopy. In this sense, the chemical specificity has converted this technique in an emerging tool for the analysis of chemical interactions and composition at the cell level. At present, Raman spectroscopy as a cell imaging method is a powerful technique to determine chemical and compositional information of biological material.¹⁰ Here, we show in this work, a free labeled non-invasive methodology to track the uptake and internalization of Laponite nanoparticles into J774 macrophages cell line by Confocal Raman Microscopy (CRM). The

combination of Raman spectroscopy and confocal microscopy, provides unique and valuable information about the localization of the nanoparticles, independently of other components in the cell, through its chemical fingerprint, taking advantage of the fact that the Raman spectra of Laponite and the biological molecules do not overlap. In addition, the simultaneous acquisition of Raman spectra from the cell and the nanoparticles at the same spot can provide specific information about the cellular region where the nanomaterial is located.¹¹ Moreover, this technique can verify if the nanoparticle is either inside the cell or at the surface without perturbing the nanoparticle-cell interaction by labeling or adding dyes. Even, the tracking of the nanoparticle in the biological medium can be made independently of the active principle taking the advantage of having direct information from the support itself, without having to discriminate from the drug, dye or contrast agent. Laponite nanoparticles were in-depth characterized by Transmission Electron Microscopy, X-ray Diffraction technique (XRD), Thermogravimetry and Calorimetry (TG-DSC) as well as Mass Spectroscopy (MS). Raman measurements of the particles functionalized with Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) were used to obtain a chemical fingerprint of the system. In parallel, a comparative *in vitro* study of the nanoparticle uptake was conducted by the most common CLSM technique.

Results and Discussion

Laponite characterization

Laponite is a layered smectite type clay with a low permanent negative layer charge compensated by exchangeable hydrated cations in the interlayer space. The chemical formula of laponite is $\text{Na}_{0.7}[\text{Si}_8\text{Mg}_{5.5}\text{Li}_{0.3}\text{O}_{20}(\text{OH})_4]$, made of one sheet of octahedral magnesia units sandwiched by two tetrahedral SiO_4 based sheets. Isomorphous substitutions of Mg^{2+} by Li^+ in

the octahedral sheet originate a low negative charge density compensated by hydrated Na^+ in the interlayer space. This nanoclay also has a non-permanent-pH dependent charge at the particle edges due to the protonation of structural hydroxyl groups at pH below 11.¹²

Figure 1. Representative TEM images of Laponite (a) and (c); XRD pattern of Laponite (b); and a representation of the tetrahedral and octahedral sheet of a layer (d).

More interestingly, for biomedical applications, Laponite has been reported to be non-toxic toward human cells, for instance mesenchymal stem cells. Moreover, degradation products, that include orthosilicic acid, $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$, can be normally found in the plasma at low concentrations.^{13,}

¹⁴ Figure 1 includes representative TEM images and a long-order characterization of the original

Laponite by XRD. TEM images and XRD provide information about the microstructure of the nanoclay, including morphology, particle size and homogeneity of the sample. The layered structure of Laponite and the particle hexagonal shape and size can be extrapolated from the TEM images. The layered structure is also evidenced by the X-ray pattern, which is composed by two types of reflections, general and basal, characteristic of swelling clays. General reflections (hk) are asymmetrical lines with “saw-tooth” shape, indicative of a two-dimensional order in the c -direction. Symmetrical basal ($00l$) reflections give an idea about the distance between the layers. The XRD diffractogram reveals a somewhat broad pattern due to the small size and the low crystallinity of the Laponite disks. A representation of the tetrahedral and octahedral sheet of Laponite is also included in figure 1 (d).

The Raman characteristic features associated with phyllosilicates are indicated in figure 2. Two principal regions, the hydroxyl stretching region ($3750\text{-}3550\text{ cm}^{-1}$), characteristic to the structural units, and the layer structure region ($150\text{-}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$), are amplified in the figure. The intense band situated at $\sim 3680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the $\nu(\text{Mg}_3\text{OH})$ vibrations whereas the broad band centred at $\sim 3420\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu(\text{HOH})$ interlayer or adsorbed water on the clay surface.^{15,16} The band reported at $\sim 3638\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ascribed to $\nu(\text{Mg}_2\text{LiOH})$ in its equivalent natural clay hectorite, is not observed in the spectrum, probably due to the overlapping with the water band. Finally, the less intense band situated at $\sim 3720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to structural OH groups perturbed by the interlayer cation situated in the ditrigonal hole of the tetrahedral sheet.¹⁷ In the second low wavenumber vibrational region, up to four bands can be assigned. The weak band at $\sim 1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the most intense band at $\sim 689\text{ cm}^{-1}$, corresponding to the asymmetric and symmetric $\nu(\text{SiO})$.¹⁸ However, the band situated at $\sim 366\text{ cm}^{-1}$, similar to other clays, has been ambiguously assigned in previous reports either to the Si-O vibrations or either to the $\nu(\text{Mg-O})$

vibrational mode.¹⁹ Finally, the band situated at the lowest wavenumber, at $\sim 188 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, is associated to the vibration of (MgLiO_6) groups.

Figure 2. Raman spectrum of Laponite (a); Low wavenumber vibrational region (b) and hydroxyl stretching region (c).

Protein adsorption on Laponite particles

Before the cell's administration, Laponite nanoparticles were functionalized with serum proteins (Laponite-FBS, see Materials and Methods section) covalently linked to FITC (FITC-FBS), thus with fluorescently labelled proteins. This allowed samples analysis using Confocal Raman

Microscopy. Firstly, the adsorption of different proteins to the particles has been quantitatively analyzed using TG-DSC and MS analysis. Figure 3 includes the TG-DSC of the raw Laponite and the Laponite in contact with proteins.

Figure 3. Representative TG curves of Laponite and FBS-Laponite (solid line). DSC and H₂O/CO₂ curves of Laponite and FBS-laponite (dashed-lines).

TG curve of raw Laponite exhibits two different regions; below 170 °C the mass loss is attributed to the desorption of water from the clay surface and dehydration of the interlayer sodium. The mass loss in this region is ~ 10 % and is associated with an endothermic peak in the DSC curve, confirming the hydrophilic character and the swelling nature of the clay. However, the mass loss in the second region, situated above 600 °C, is related to clay dehydroxylation, and

is also associated with an endothermic peak in the DSC curve. Finally, the dehydroxylation step is followed by an exothermic peak due to a phase transition above 700 °C corresponding to rapid recrystallization of the clay.²⁰ The water loss has been also followed by mass spectroscopy and included in figure 3. The dehydration and dehydroxylation processes are accompanied by a maximum in the water curve. In contrast, TG analysis of Laponite after being in contact with FBS presents three different regions as it is expected for organo-clays.²¹ Besides the two regions described above, a third region between 170 °C and 500 °C can be observed as a result of the thermal reactions suffered by the proteins adsorbed on the clay surface. The mass loss steps in this region are accompanied by characteristic exothermic peaks from the oxidation of the organic matter. This third region, characteristic of the combustion process, is prolonged to the dehydroxylation region, due to a deficit of oxygen in the atmosphere used during the experiment. The DSC exothermic peaks coincide with two maxima in the CO₂ curve measured by mass spectroscopy. The first mass loss step (below 170 °C) of the Laponite in contact with FBS decreases up to ~ 6.5 %, due to the protein adsorption, being the water content an indirect evidence of the less hydrophilic character of the clay surface. The content of the protein in the sample can be calculated from the second mass loss step and it is around 24 % of the sample mass. Similar results have been obtained from the Laponite in contact with FITC bound to serum proteins (non-shown).

In order to administrate Laponite to the macrophages, the nanoclay must be resuspended in FBS. Three samples, i.e. raw FBS, Laponite and Laponite suspended in 30 % of FBS were analyzed by Raman spectroscopy for comparison. This technique combines several advantages; on the one hand, Raman spectroscopy can determine chemical structures via vibrational spectra; as a result, cells, proteins and other biological material do not need to be labelled prior imaging; and on the

other hand, since water has a weak Raman signal, cells can be imaged in aqueous media, under normal physiological conditions.²²

Figure 4. Raman spectrum of FBS with the main peaks assigned (a); and comparison of the Raman spectra of Laponite, raw FBS and Laponite-FBS where the peak at 689 cm⁻¹ and 3680 cm⁻¹ have been marked respectively, with a black arrow (b and c).

Firstly, figure 4a shows the Raman spectrum of FBS. The Raman signal collected in the spectral interval of (200-1800) cm⁻¹, also called the fingerprint region, is considered the most representative region for biomolecules while the most intensive array of bands appears in the

spectrum between 2700 and 3100 cm^{-1} . This group of bands is related to a complex interaction between C-H stretching modes, overlaid with methylene and methyl group stretching modes, mainly from lipids and proteins.²³

The rest of the bands in the spectrum correspond to proteins (or amino acids), lipids and water, which are the main components of serum. Despite a lot of biochemical information present in the spectra due to the complex nature of Raman spectra of biological materials, the most representative peaks of the FBS sample have been assigned in Figure 4a.²⁴ It is worth noting that two Raman zones of proteins are present in the spectrum of FBS: (1) bands relating to the peptide backbone and (2) bands relating to the amino acids side chains.²⁵ Respect to the peptide backbone, the α -helix amide I band is situated near 1655 cm^{-1} while the band corresponding to the amide III (α -helix or random) is at $\sim 1260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Aromatic amino acids Phe, Tyr and Trp show characteristic bands at $\sim 1608 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 1008 cm^{-1} , 857 cm^{-1} and 621 cm^{-1} . The region of 550-500 cm^{-1} contains bands of S-S stretching vibrations of disulfide bonds, related to Cys. Fatty acids can be distinguished by a typical band at 1440 cm^{-1} . Finally, the peak at $\sim 1338 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to the resonance vibration of Trp residues overlapping by the band of CH bending vibrations. Secondly, the Raman spectrum of Laponite functionalized with FBS (see figure 4b and c) is analyzed and compared to initial FBS and Laponite. The characteristic peaks of Laponite previously identified in figure 2, i.e. the one at 689 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the asymmetric and symmetric $\nu(\text{SiO})$, and the one at 3680 cm^{-1} , attributed to the $\nu(\text{Mg}_3\text{OH})$ vibrations -, clearly appear in the Laponite-FBS spectrum (black arrows) as well resolved and independent peaks. This result demonstrates that the Raman spectroscopy is a suitable technique to detect Laponite when it is dispersed in a complex mixture of biomolecules such as serum.

Intracellular uptake of Laponite

As pointed out in the introduction, a key aspect in the study of nanoplateforms in biomedicine is to univocally confirm the intracellular uptake of the nanomaterial. For this purpose, indirect methods like fluorescence microscopy are used to detect the nanoparticles, which must be previously stained with fluorescent label, within a cell. Labelling the nanoparticle is complicated, and it usually requires chemical procedures that can affect the surface chemistry of the nanoparticle. We have demonstrated in the previous section that Raman spectroscopy represents an excellent alternative to track the free labelled Laponite. Thus, in this section, the presence and interaction mechanisms of the nanoclay in macrophage cells is studied using Raman spectroscopy.

Unlike other techniques, Raman spectroscopy is a non-invasive and label-free technique that allows us to directly monitor the nanoparticle in the cell by following its chemical fingerprint. Moreover, the combination of a Raman spectrometer with a confocal microscope allows both imaging and mapping of cells by acquiring hundreds of full Raman spectra sequentially across the sample instead of doing independent point-spectrum at one particular location.²² The Raman image is constructed according to the relative intensity of each band in the spectrum at each point.

Firstly, representative Raman spectra of a control macrophage were acquired along the cell and included in figure 5. A bright-field image of the macrophage indicating the points (from numbers 1 to 6) where the Raman spectra were taken, are also in the figure. Similar to the FBS sample, the six spectra exhibit the two intense bands at $\sim 2885\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the vibrational stretching region of the hydrocarbon chain structure (CH_2) of lipids, and the CH_3 stretching band at 2935 cm^{-1} . The Raman signals attributed to proteins (S-S, Phe, Tyr, Trp, Amide III, Amide I), lipids (CH , CH_2 , CH_3), or water (OH) are also present in the spectra. The ring breathing vibrations modes attributed to DNA and RNA bases appear at 784 cm^{-1} in the spectrum with the symmetric PO_2^- stretching vibration of the DNA backbone at $\sim 1093\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Differences in

the intensities of the peaks are observed between the six spectra depending on the local composition of the sample; for instance, the peaks corresponding to DNA or PO_2^- are mostly in the nuclei, spectrum which corresponds to point number one.

Moreover, figure 5c and 5d show the amplification of both regions, the hydroxyl stretching region and low wavenumber vibrational region. No bands can be distinguished in the spectra at $\sim 689 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 3680 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Thus, this result also demonstrates that there is no overlapping between the Raman peaks of Laponite and cells.

Secondly, according to viability assays (figure S1), a biocompatible $200 \mu\text{g/mL}$ doses of functionalized Laponite were administrated to macrophages. Those cultures were analysed by Raman spectroscopy after 24 h (figure 6) and 48 h (figure S2).

Figure 5. Bright-field image of a macrophage (a); Raman spectra of the 6 points indicated in the macrophage image (b); Raman spectra of the hydroxyl stretching region of the macrophage (c) Raman spectra of the low wavenumber vibrational region of the macrophage (d). The blue lines point out the lack of peaks in the region of 689 cm^{-1} and 3680 cm^{-1}

Figure 6. Bright-field image of a macrophage after 24 h of the Laponite-FBS administration (scale bar 5 μm). Peak integrated images of the 689 cm^{-1} band (green), 3680 cm^{-1} band (orange) of Laponite and 784 cm^{-1} band (blue) of nuclei. The image on the right represents the overlapping of the three previous images (a). Four examples of Raman spectra indicating the presence of Laponite inside the macrophage (blue, orange and green spectra) and a cell area with no Laponite (red).

The first image shown in Figure 6a is a bright-field image of a macrophage after 24 h of the Laponite-FBS administration where its contouring can be observed. The other three images in figure 6a are made by mapping the cell, detecting the relative intensity of specific bands associated with Laponite at 689 cm^{-1} and 3680 cm^{-1} , and with nuclei by detecting the intensity of the 784 cm^{-1} band associated with phosphodiester bond of nucleic acids.²⁶ The peak integrated intensity images obtained from both the 689 cm^{-1} , (in green in the figure), and the 3680 cm^{-1} bands (in orange in the figure) give an identical distribution of Laponite particles in the cell. In the

overlapped image on the right the location of the nuclei, and the distribution of the Laponite particles can be observed all over the cell. After 24 h incubation, the intracellular uptake of Laponite nanoparticles can be confirmed. Green and orange dots associated with Raman Laponite signals can be clearly observed in the image. Unlike other studies in which the internalization of the nanoclay has been assumed by indirect methods, for example by measuring the fluorescence signal of an active drug adsorbed on the clay surface like doxorubicin;⁶ Our Raman imaging methodology allows us to univocally characterize the nanoparticle cell uptake and processing, measuring the unique chemical fingerprint of the nanopatform. In brief, figure 6 shows that Raman spectroscopy is sensitive enough to detect the Laponite signalling not only when it is dispersed in serum, but also in cell cultures, giving a clear image of the nanoparticles and its location inside the macrophage. The numbers included in the bright-field image are four examples of different spectra represented at the bottom of the figure 6b. The first three spectra correspond to three representative points of the macrophage where Laponite is found. While the fourth spectrum (red) corresponds to a control example in which the characteristic peaks of Laponite at 689 cm^{-1} and 3680 cm^{-1} are not observed. It can be verified that at this particular location there are not Laponite particles inside the cell. Also, the simultaneous acquisition of Raman signals from the cell and nanoparticle from the same spot allows identifying the cellular region where the Laponite is located. The stretching bands of CH_2 at 2850 cm^{-1} are much more intense in the lipid bodies than the CH_3 stretching bands at 2935 cm^{-1} , and on the contrary, the last signal is more intense in the cytoplasm due to the relative lower content of CH_2 groups in proteins. Laponite signals are present in the spectra with intense CH_3 stretching modes, typical for proteins, indicating that nanoparticles are localized in the cytosol. Moreover, the peak that corresponds to the phosphodiester bond at 784 cm^{-1} , associated with the nuclei is only present in the control spectrum.

Figure 7. Bright-field image of a macrophage after 24 h of the Lap-FBS administration (scale bar 5 μm). Three graphics (representing three different points in the cell) of the integrated intensity of the peak at 689 cm^{-1} in all the Z-planes (a); Scheme of the Z-planes at different focal distances in the macrophage (b); Overlapping of the peak integrated intensity images of the 689 cm^{-1} band of Laponite (green) and the 784 cm^{-1} band of the nucleus (blue) bands at three Z-planes, (scale bar 5 μm) (c).

Finally, to double-check the internalization of the nanoclay in the macrophage and to discard a possible adhesion of Laponite to the membrane surface of the cell, a mapping of intracellular structures was performed by acquiring Raman spectra at different focal positions (Z-planes). Figure 7 includes a study of the in-depth intracellular composition by the Raman acquisition of a several planes in the z-direction. Confocal Raman spectroscopy can track the Laponite nanoparticles position and study the distribution in the cell by performing different Raman spectra at different Z-planes (with 300 nm distance between them) in the same spot, and by comparison with the relative intensity of the characteristic Laponite bands. For this purpose, the integrated intensity of the Laponite peak at 689 cm^{-1} is represented at each focal distance in figure 7a. In all

cases, as was shown in Figure 6, the Laponite signature is accompanied by intense CH₃ stretching bands, typical for proteins. The low intensity of the CH₂ stretching bands in the spectra indicates that Laponite is not associated with lipid bodies. Moreover, the absence of the typical signal attributed to DNA at 784 cm⁻¹ in the Laponite spectrum evidences the not internalization of the nanodispenser in the cell nucleus. As it can be observed in the figure 7a, the peak area/intensity is not constant over the scan planes, being higher in the planes situated in a distance range of (0.9-2.6) μm from the focus. This figure demonstrates that the Z-scanning can to unambiguously prove the internalization of the nanoparticles in the cell, being the confocal Raman spectroscopy a very useful technique to detect nanomaterials within cells or organisms, as a free-labeled methodology. Finally, Laponite particles adhesion phenomena to the cell membrane can be discharged attending the maximum relative intensity of the Laponite peaks acquired at the different Z-planes.

To illustrate that point, figure 7c includes three mapping at different Z-planes after the phagocytosis of Laponite particles by the macrophage; one closer to the cell surface, another in the centre of the cell and the last one proximate to the cover's surface, according to the scheme (figure 7c). The images represented in figure 6 have been selected from the mapping at different Z-planes according to the location of Laponite particles in the cell (plane number 2 of figure 7).

Figure 8. Fluorescence confocal images after the administration of Laponite functionalized with FBS-FITC. The images of the left correspond to a Z confocal projection of the cell culture. The images of the right represent a single confocal Z-plane. Lateral Z-projection images are shown at the right and bottom of the images. The white cross in the XY and lateral Z projection images indicates the localization of an intracellular Laponite cluster (green channel). The cellular cytoplasm are stained with propidium iodide (red channel) and nuclei with Hoescht. The scale bar is 20 μm (24 h) and 50 μm (48 h).

For comparison purposes, Laponite nanoparticles were stained with fluorescent FBS (FBS-FITC, see Material and Methods section) to study the uptake and processing of the nanoparticle in the cell with CLSM, and to compare the results with Raman spectroscopy. Previous studies carried out with Laponites nanoparticles functionalized with the fluorescent drug doxorubicin describe the internalization of the hybrid materials in the cytosol and cell nuclei, by following the autofluorescence of the drug by the red dots observed in both cell regions. Also, nanomaterial

clustering on the cell membrane has been suggested.⁶ The tracking of the nanoparticle's cell uptake was obtained by an indirect method, and the adhesion of the nanoparticle doxorubicin along with the nanoparticles uptake and processing mechanism have been assumed. Figure 8 includes the CLSM images of macrophages after 24 h and 48 h of the administration of the FBS-FITC functionalized Laponite nanoparticles (in green). In the image, functionalized Laponite particles can be seen on macrophages, in particular they appear inside the cytosol, however, the internalization of the nanoparticles cannot be unambiguously determined from that image.

Confocal microscopy lateral projection images serve to determine the intracellular localization of the nanomaterial (white crosses), this confirming that Laponite is localised inside the cytoplasm of the cell. The same occurs at 48 h, although there is less amount of Laponite in cells. This phenomenon can be explained due to the fast division rate of macrophages; as cells divide, the nanomaterials remain constant, thus, having at the end, less quantify of nanomaterial per cell.

Conclusions

The internalization process of the Laponite nanodispenser into macrophage has been documented using confocal Raman microscopy. Unlike conventional techniques, such as the most commonly used CMLS, the combination of Raman spectroscopy and confocal microscopy, provides unique and direct information about the localization of the nanoparticle within the cell by its unique chemical fingerprint. Firstly, we have shown that the Raman spectroscopy can distinguish Laponite when it is dispersed in a complex mixture of biomolecules such as serum. The characteristic peaks of Laponite - at 689 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the asymmetric and symmetric $\nu(\text{SiO})$, and at 3680 cm^{-1} attributed to the $\nu(\text{Mg}_3\text{OH})$ vibrations -, clearly appear in the Laponite-FBS spectrum as well resolved and independent peaks. Secondly, the combination of the Raman technique with a confocal microscope allows mapping the cells by acquiring full Raman spectra

sequentially across the sample and to construct an image according to the integrated intensity of Laponite bands in the spectrum at every point. Hence, the distribution of Laponite particles can be discriminated all over the cell. Besides, the simultaneous acquisition of Raman spectra from the cell and nanoparticles from the same spot allows us identifying whether Laponite is located in the cytosol or associated with other cellular parts, like lipid bodies or nuclei. Finally, the acquisition of Raman spectra at different Z-planes allows us to proof the heterogeneous in-depth distribution of Laponite particles in the cell. This free-label Raman imaging methodology is an ideal technique to follow the cell uptake and processing of the nanodispenser nanoclay Laponite.

Material and Methods

Characterization of Laponite

Laponite (provided by BYK-Chemie GmbH) has been characterized using Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM, with a JEOL JEM 1011 microscope), X-ray diffractometer (with a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA, in a Setaram Setsys evolution TGA–DTA/DSC model). Raman measurements were performed with a JASCO NRS-4500 Confocal Raman Microscope under 532 nm excitation wavelength. The light is collected with a 100x objective and dispersed with a 900 grooves/mm grating and detected with an Andor Newton CCD detector refrigerated with Peltier at -70 °C.

Functionalization of Laponite

To have a well-dispersed dissolution of Laponite, 200 µg/mL of Laponite were resuspended in 30 % Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) by mild sonication. Aggregates were taken out by centrifugation at 1000 rpm for 15 minutes. For fluorescence confocal imaging, Laponite was

functionalized with FBS conjugated with Fluorescein Isothiocyanate Isomer I (FITC, from Sigma-Aldrich, ref: 34321-1GM-M). To obtain FITC-FBS, a mixture of bicarbonate with FBS and FITC was incubated for 1 h at RT protected from light. The excess of FITC was cleaned with a PD-10 desalting column, with Sephadex G-25 resin (from GE Healthcare Life Sciences™, ref: 17085101). The fluorescent protein was eluted in filtered phosphate saline buffer (PBS).

Cell culture, Confocal Raman spectroscopy and confocal microscopy

J774 A1 murine macrophage cells (from the European Molecular Biology Laboratory Cell Bank) were cultured under standard conditions in Iscove's Modified Dulbecco's Medium (IMDM, from Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific, ref: 12440053) containing 10 % FBS and antibiotics (from Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Cells were incubated with 200 µg/mL of functionalized and washed Laponite. For Raman spectroscopy cells were grown in CaF₂ coverslips for 24 h and 48 h to avoid the Raman peaks overlap of the normal glass slides with the cells and Laponite. Cells were fixed with 10 % neutral buffered formalin (with approximately 4 % of formaldehyde) (from Sigma-Aldrich, ref: HT501128-4L). Subsequently, they were let to dry and analyzed with the Jasco NRS 4500. For fluorescence confocal imaging, cells were grown in borosilicate coverslips and after 24 h and 48 h they were fixed in 4 % paraformaldehyde. Nuclei and cells were stained with Hoechst dye (from Sigma-Aldrich, ref: 94403) and propidium iodide (from Sigma-Aldrich, ref: P4170), respectively. Confocal microscopy images were obtained with a Nikon A1R confocal microscope and were processed with the NIS-Elements Advanced Research software. All confocal cell images are pseudo-colored. Viability of macrophages was analysed by quantifying the necrotic cells using the Trypan Blue dye (from Sigma Aldrich, re: T8154). Cells were quantified with the TC20™ Automates Cell Counter (from Bio Rad).

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank IDIVAL for financial support, Projects N°NVAL16/17, INNVAL19/18 and NVAL18/07. CRL thanks the MINECO for the Juan de la Cierva Formación grant (ref. FJCI-2015-25306). This work has been supported by the Spanish MINECO, Instituto de Salud Carlos III, the European Union FEDER funds under Projects ref. PI16/00496 (AES 2016), PI19/00349 and DTS19/00033 (AES 2019).

ABBREVIATIONS

CLSM, Confocal Laser Scanning Microscope; TEM, Transmission electron microscopy; CRM, Confocal Raman Microscopy; XRD, X-ray Diffraction technique; TG-DSC, Calorimetry, MS, Mass Spectroscopy; FBS, Fetal Bovine Serum; FITC-BSA, fluorescent labelled proteins.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Supporting information available: Macrophage survival upon exposure to 200 µg/mL of Laponite with not statistically significant differences (figure S1). Raman Mapping of a macrophage after 48 h of the administration of Laponite (figure S2).

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